

THE INFLUENCE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THINKING ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE METHODOLOGY OF TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: This thesis is dedicated to studying the role and importance of thinking development technologies in the educational system. In particular, methods of developing students' creative and critical thinking are analyzed with the help of technological education methods. Modern pedagogical technologies and possibilities of increasing their efficiency are considered. The article shows the influence of methods that help to acquire practical knowledge more deeply through the technologies of thinking development in the educational process.

Key words: development of thinking, technological education, methodology, pedagogical technologies, creative thinking, critical thinking, educational efficiency, practical knowledge.

Introduction:

In the modern educational process, the development of students' thinking is of great importance. Today, technological advances and innovative approaches are widely used at every stage of education, requiring students to develop not only the level of knowledge, but also the ability to think independently. In particular, the pedagogical methods used in the field of technological education have a great impact on the formation of creative and critical thinking of students. In this process, the learning process of students can be more effective and interesting through modern information technologies, interactive methods and practical exercises. Therefore, the development of thinking as an integral part of technological education serves as an important tool for increasing the efficiency of the modern educational process.

Literature review:

Scientific studies on the development of thinking and the methodology of technological education show that there are serious changes and innovations in this direction. Pedagogical literature contains many theoretical and practical studies about the nature of the thinking process, its formation and development. In particular, the theory of "reflective thinking" put forward by Dewey (1910) is important in the formation of students' ability to think independently in the educational process. Dewey's ideas have not lost their relevance even today, on

the contrary, they are more widely used in the process of technological education.

Also, in the theory of "cultural-historical development" of Vygotsky (1934), it is emphasized that the formation of thinking is carried out through language and culture, which helps to understand the specific features of imparting knowledge with the help of technological means. Modern researchers, including Perkins (1995) and Salomon (1990), emphasize the effectiveness of using technology in the development of thinking processes and emphasize the advantages of methods based on interactive approaches to students' learning.

The analysis of Uzbek and foreign literature shows that the introduction of pedagogical technologies into the educational process increases the effectiveness of education and develops the creative thinking of students. For example, the research of M. V. Klarin (1995) analyzes the didactic and psychological foundations of technological education and reveals its role in the development of creativity in students. At the same time, the works of A. A. Poskryakov on the development of innovative consciousness, widely illuminate the influence of technologies in the formation of new thinking skills of students.

The analysis of this literature allows for a deeper understanding of the interaction of the main approaches and methods in the improvement of the technological education methodology and the development of students' thinking.

Discussion:

Researches and practices carried out within the framework of technological education methodology for the development of thinking have a significant impact on the educational process. Teaching students to think independently is one of the central goals of the pedagogical process today. The methods used in technological education play an important role in the realization of this goal, because they encourage students not only to acquire ready-made knowledge, but also to form creative and critical approaches.

The rapid development of modern information and communication technologies opens up new opportunities for pedagogues. Interactive teaching tools, simulations and digital learning platforms provide effective ways to develop students' thinking. These tools help students enrich their practical knowledge and find creative solutions to real-life problems.

However, there are some difficulties in the practical application of technological education. For example, using technology incorrectly or using it only as a means of information transfer can limit students' creative thinking

rather than develop it. Therefore, didactically and methodologically correct and effective use of technologies in pedagogical approaches is required. The training and experience of teachers in the use of technologies is also of great importance in this process.

The analysis shows that the correct organization of technological educational tools and the selection of appropriate methods give significant results in the development of creative and critical thinking of students. This is one of the main tasks of the modern education system - to teach students not only ready-made knowledge, but also an important factor in the formation of their independent and creative thinking.

Conclusion:

The development of thinking is important as an integral part of the educational process within the technological education methodology. The possibilities of developing students' creative and critical thinking are expanding through the use of modern pedagogical approaches and technologies. As stated in this article, the correct organization of technological education not only increases the quality of education, but also develops students' ability to solve problems in real life. At the same time, for the effective use of technologies in the educational process, pedagogues themselves must be ready for modern approaches.

In the future, by further improving technological education, the development of students' independent thinking, problem analysis and creative approach skills will be one of the most important tasks of education. Thus, the technological education methodology serves as an important tool in increasing the efficiency of the modern educational process and in the comprehensive development of students.

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